

SOCIAL SCIENCES

COAST POLLUTION IN ALBANIA AND ITS SOCIAL PROBLEMS

Darina Çoni (Kacollja),

*Lecturer at the Faculty of Education,
'Aleksandër Xhuvani' University, Elbasan 3001, Albania*

Albana Madhi

*Lecturer at the Faculty of Economy,
'Aleksandër Xhuvani' University, Elbasan 3001 Albania*

Abstract

Coast pollution is one of the main problems especially in developing countries. This study represents the coastal pollution due to the unsolicited and unprotected development of these areas. Construction of residential, hotels etc in these areas without first having infrastructure built, especially the sewerage, will bring about an increase in pollution in these areas. This study was based on 19 interviews conducted by residents who bought buildings in these areas but also people who were involved in the construction of these facilities, such as investors, engineers, etc. This study extends to an area that lies between Durres and Kavaja in Albania. These interviews represent the state of coastal pollution. It is one of the main causes that formed the conviction of the vacationers who frequented these areas that the waters of these areas are very polluted. This made these areas not to be frequented as before. This reduction has reduced prices but also the reduction of employees in the tourism sector. This study also represents the change of this condition in the period when this infrastructure was realized. The pollution reduction became possible, but the removal of the concept from the holidaymakers that this area is no longer polluted, is more difficult. This area continues to be mentioned as one of the most problematic areas of Albania.

Keywords: Albania, environmental pollution, coast, construction.

1. Introduction

Albania is located in the southwestern area of the Balkan Peninsula and its coastal area is over 400 km long.[1] As Garten, L. points out: coastal areas are waters near the coast and adjacent land areas. Globally, coastal areas are from the most dynamic and rapid change environments.[2] Being a coastal area, there should be a lot of benefits, especially in tourism. [3] Tourism is one of the most profitable branches, especially in the developing area. As Boero points out: Naval and coastal ecosystems provide essential goods and services that support communities and economies, including food safety, recreational opportunities and other benefits.[4]

These benefits are reduced when you fail to manage the development of the coastal area. This lack of management will bring about the underdevelopment of major branches such as tourism and fishing. As Fisher points out: Coastal communities in all developing countries suffer from high levels of poverty and low levels of education.[5] This study was based on the area between Durres and Kavaja, where before 1990 it was one of the best tourism areas. This is one of the areas where after 1990 it was built more. From 2005 to 2011, only in the Prefecture of Durres have been granted construction permits for buildings with a construction surface of 1,441.000 m². [6]

This uncontrolled construction brought a lot of problems; pollution is one of these problems. Unplanned expansion of rural and urban areas is a widespread phenomenon in Albania.[7] This study highlights the pollution of this area, as well as some of the causes that lead to the pollution of this area.

In 2016, the study conducted by the Ministry of Environment shows that the area from Durres to Kavaja continues to be the most polluted.[8] As well, the Municipality of Durres in 2015 points out that Durres beach continues to have a problem with pollution. The Durres sewage system (special system) was built before the 1990s for a population of 90,000. In those times the connection to the service was 100%. During 1993 to 2007 very limited investments were made in the sewer system, the share of families related to sewage networks is on average 55% in the city. Rural areas have no sewage network. The main way of depositing sewage, especially in informal areas, as well as at 5 NJA are septic pits, the overwhelming of these septic pits go into the agricultural drainage channels with insufficient capacity.[9] This study reveals the reasons why this area became one of the most polluted areas in Albania. Although there is an environmental protection legislation, this is not in many cases appropriate. Unfortunately, the implementation of the existing environmental protection legislation in Albania is often absent due to the lack of experience, low awareness or imperfect staff of local government bodies.[10] The study also highlights the negative impact that this pollution had on the tourism industry. The spread of the fact that this area is polluted brought about the decrease in the number of holidaymakers as well as the lowering of hotel prices, restaurants. Reducing prices was the only way to survive in this area.

The study also represents the change of this area after it has been completed and the underground network has been used, including the sewage network. The construction of this network reduced the pollution of

this area, bringing about the growth of tourists resting in the area.

2. Theoretical Framework

As Diaz Eta points out (2015): Nature contributes to the quality of human life but at the same time, human developments have caused significant loss in biodiversity through overhaul and other promoters of change.[11] It is difficult to justify the preservation of biodiversity without demonstrating its benefits to people[12]

Effective environmental management and protection help maintain high productivity and high diversity in marine systems, protecting social and economic developments.[13] Community - based natural resource management is designed not only to maintain biodiversity but also to soften poverty [13]

While the success of the planning process is ensured by the balanced involvement of the stakeholders, the success of the implementation phase depends on the well - defined incentives for local communities. [12]

Our relationship with coastal areas is a delicate relationship, we get numerous benefits but we have important impacts on the systems approaching these benefits.[14]

3. Methodology

This study used qualitative methodology. When researchers have little information and require rigorous exploration of the research problem learning from participants, quality research is appropriate. [15] For this study, 14 interviews were conducted, with persons who were involved in the construction of these facilities in this area. Participants were randomly selected within this frame. The questions were combined, closed and open questions as well. Open questions were used in order to give the interviewees the opportunity to describe new information about topics that were of interest. These research conversations lasted from 25 to 35 minutes. They were assured that whatever information they shared would be kept confidential. To preserve their identity, we do not mention their names. Upon completion of the interviews, which were recorded, their transcription and manual coding in vivo began.[16]

4. Result

Construction was one of the industries that took a lot of development after 1991 and was one of the most profitable branches. There were given thousands of permits, the area where there was no construction before, now were overcrowded by the constructions. It also spread to the illegal constructions, the phenomenon of building where it was possible, until 2013 was prevailing. Not even the coastal areas were saved from this wave. This phenomenon is also emphasized during the interview.

Question, that if many residential buildings were built, or hotels in these areas. One resident, among other things, points out that more were built in these areas than inside the city. If before 1990, the area from Plepa to Qerret had no constructions, except for a greenery area, this area became a small town because of constructions.

While, another resident points out, construction in the area became disturbing, if someone bought an apartment overlooking at the sea, it did not pass long when you see a palace being built in front and blocking the view.

What did the inhabitants of the palace do? At first there were protests, even in front of the municipality, prevented machinery from working. But the facility was on a permit from the municipality and could not be obstructed by force, so it was built. But, in many cases, residents could not stop building the facility even when it was without permission. This brought no one to protest anymore.

Questions why so many construction permits were given in these areas.

A contractor emphasizes; The sales of apartments in these areas were very fast. At the beginning, as long as the pits were opened to build the foundations, a good portion of the apartments of the palace were sold. This made it possible for the companies' profits to be high.

Questions how these companies could get permission in these areas, being coastal areas. One resident points out: These companies with their acquaintances were able to press in the municipality to obtain a building permit in these areas. This was justified by the situation where there was no development plan by the municipality for this area. Instead of prohibiting construction until a plan was made, the opposite was made, they were given permission without criteria.

Questions that if objects without construction permits were able to be built in this area. One technician who had worked in this area states: I can say that they were built a lot, it was difficult to stop, there was no will on the part of state structures to operate. Illegal construction was common throughout Albania, especially after 1997.

Whereas one resident points out, illegal construction exploded after 1991, you can say that more buildings were built without permission than with permission. Not only small villas but palaces as well were allowed to be constructed without permission. These unlawful mansions were also built by the sea. But what about these objects, were they demolished over time?

Another resident states: you can not talk about demolishing, they were all legalized and became lawful, although at first there were voices that would that would not be legalization of illegal constructions in coastal areas.

Since the infrastructure was missing, the people who bought these apartments, either were not informed about the lack of underground infrastructure, or believed it would be regulated very quickly.

One resident of these palaces points out among other things that when he bought the apartment he did not know where the sewage was spilled. He learned it later when he started using the apartment. He saw the position of the palace near the sea and the interior part of apartment, liked it and he didn't deal with the rest.

Another resident points out that he knew they did not have the necessary infrastructure but hoped to be regulated. Once the necessary infrastructure is adjusted and the price of the apartments will increase.

Another resident, among other things, says: I did not know that the palace I bought had illegal floors, nor did I know where the black waters were unloaded and where they took the water. These came out after the palace is over and we entered to live in.

Unplanned urbanization and without being accompanied by an engineering infrastructure, such as the sewage network, water supply, roads, would also be associated with an increase in pollution. In 2006, Durrës had 85 % of clean beaches but in 2009 it went to 69 %.[17] Durrës was one of the prefectures with polluted beaches.

From the interview, some reasons were given why these coastal areas were more polluted. Thus, although these construction companies, at the time of construction of the buildings, due to the lack of sewage, they built septic pits. These pits were not under technical conditions.

Thus, an engineer about 70 years old who had been involved in these areas states: in coastal areas, especially from Plepa area to Qereti area, the underground infrastructure was missing, starting with the water supply and sewage network.

Construction companies, although building septic tanks, these pits were not under technical conditions, enabling the black waters to pollute the environment, making this area smell terribly during the summer.

Regarding the way of building these septic pits, a technician that had worked in the area points out: These septic pits were not done with enforced concrete and to be waterproofed so that they were not filtered, but were made outside of technical conditions. They were made with bricks or blocks without waterproofing in order to filter sewage. These septic pits were related to the palace that was constructed. All the polluted water filtered through the sand and ended in groundwater and sea.

Another states that septic pits were made with bricks and not only were not waterproofing but their floor was left as it was, sand, to filter the water.

There were some investors who went so far as to make it possible for these septic tanks to discharge into the sea, making it possible for these pits to discharge into the sea through an underground pipe. The control of the state bodies at this point was almost non-existent.

Question about whether there were facilities that discharged sewage directly into the sea. A resident of the area points out that: almost everyone in the sea pours septic tanks in that period, the septic tanks were just to say: yes, we have septic tanks.

While an other shows that almost all the facilities that were in the first line, to avoid the bad smell coming from the septic tanks, connected the facility with pipes under the sand up to several meters into the sea.

Meanwhile, another resident says that there were so many buildings that poured the black water directly into the sea, that in that period they were advertised for shares by the state institutions to cut these pipes, which were poured into the sea, but without effects.

Despite the fact that the pollution was high, there were many people visiting the area for summer vacations.

Question if there were many vacationers who frequented this coastline for vacations during that period?

Among other things, one resident emphasizes: there were many people, although it was said that it was one of the most polluted areas.

While another emphasizes: they frequented it a lot, also because of the lower prices, from hotel rooms to restaurants.

While another resident emphasizes that there was a lot of attendance, this was due to the lack of road infrastructure to go to other areas.

The construction of the sewage network and the sewage treatment plan brought an increase in the quality of the beaches in this area. But there are still some other problems.

Question about whether the situation changed after the sewerage and water supply network was completed.

A resident point out: of course, the black water is no longer poured into the sea, the septic tanks are destroyed and all the buildings are connected to the sewage network, this brought an increase in the quality of the beaches in this area.

And another resident emphasizes that this resulted in these beaches being pollution-free. The area began to be frequented by more vacationers.

Another resident, among other things, says that some areas continue to be polluted. Especially the areas, where the water of the streams flows into the sea. These small streams bring the waters of the areas that are close by pouring them into the sea.

Discussion:

This qualitative study highlights the pollution of coastal areas from uncontrolled and not well-planned development. Many coastal areas are at risk due to the harmful effects of increased urban sprawl, industrial pollution and sewage discharges.[2]

As this study shows, the construction of many facilities without building the underground network brought an increase in pollution in sea waters. In the area of Durrës, the beaches near Torres, Plepa and the former Camp of Pioneers are particularly polluted, about 10 times more the allowed rate. In the MMPAU report, it is emphasized that of the 21 beaches observed in Durrës, 90% are classified as Poor Quality and 10% of them as Sufficient Quality. These conclusions list Durrës as the area with the most polluted beaches in the country.[18]

This uncontrolled development was not accompanied by a control of state institutions for the control of environmental pollution, in this way the construction companies benefited from this situation and did not implement the minimum conditions for septic tanks. While the state institutions blamed each other.[19] As Christen points out: Urban flow is also increasing as land is converted to urban and sub-urban use at a rate much faster than the rate of population growth [20] This also leads to an increase in the pollution of coastal areas.

This situation changed a lot when the sewer network and road infrastructure were completed in this area. In 2021, according to the European Union's report on the quality of marine waters in the city of Durrës, only 2 areas have polluted waters [21].

Conclusions:

The central and local state institutions should not urbanize an area, especially the coastal areas, without first completing the underground network such as that of black waters and water pipes, but they should also build roads and the electrical network, urbanize the area. Otherwise, this will be accompanied by an increase in polluted coastal areas. The regeneration of these areas takes time.

Also, state institutions should take measures for canals and streams that flow into the sea. The sewage of rural areas or the waters of industrial enterprises must not be poured into these waters, as these waters pollute the marine area where they are poured.

References

1. BREW, D S. Geomorphology of the Albanian Adriatic Coast: A Study of Short-and Long-term Changes at Karavasta Lagoon and their Implications for Coastal Management. 2003. *Geography*, 88(2), 88–98. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40573827>.
2. Garten L. The Coastal Zone Management Act: A Mixed Success. 2016. *Consilience*, 16, 1–13. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26188770>.
3. Pikelj, K., & Juračić, M. Eastern Adriatic Coast (EAC): Geomorphology and Coastal Vulnerability of a Karstic Coast. 2013. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 29(4), 944–957. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23486562>.
4. Boero, F & Bonsdorff E “A conceptual framework for marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning” *marine ecology Volume 28 issue s1 september 2007* pages 134-145.
5. Fisher, B., Ellis, A. M., Adams, D. K., Fox, H. E., & Selig, E. R. Health, wealth, and education: the socioeconomic backdrop for marine conservation in the developing world. 2015. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 530, 233–242.
6. Instituti i Statistikave http://databaza.instat.gov.al/pxweb/sq/DST/START__ND__NDY/NDY003/table/tableViewLayout1/
7. Polemio, M., Pambuku, A., Limoni, P. P., & Petrucci, O. Carbonate Coastal Aquifer of Vlora Bay and Groundwater Submarine Discharge (Southwestern Albania). 2011. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 26–34. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25790511>.
8. *Journal Health* 2016. <https://shendeti.com.al/harta-e-plazheve-me-te-pastradhe-me-te-ndotura-ne-shqiperi/>
9. Durres Municipality Territorial Development Strategy 2015-2030. http://www.km.dldp.al/wp-multimedia/st/durres/Strategjia_e_Zhvillimit_Territorial_2015-2030_Aneks.pdf
10. Cullaj, A., Hasko, B., Miho, A., Schanz, F., Brandle, H. and Bachofen, R. The Quality of Albanian Natural Waters and the Human Impact. 2005. *Environment International*, 31, 133-146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2004.06.008>
11. Díaz S et al. The IPBES Conceptual Framework — connecting nature and people, *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, [2015] 1-16
12. Laušević, R., & Bartula, M. Participatory Planning for Biodiversity Protection in the Western Balkans. 2016. *Natural Areas Journal*, 36(3), 339–344.
13. Frascchetti, S., Terlizzi, A., Eta. Effects of Unplanned Development on Marine Biodiversity: A Lesson from Albania (Central Mediterranean Sea). 2011. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 106–115.
14. Yoskowitz, D., & Russell. Human Dimensions of Our Estuaries and Coasts. *Estuaries and Coasts*. 2015.38, S1–S8. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44851304>
15. Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. 2015. San Francisco, CA: Wiley.
16. Saldana, J. *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 2016. Sage Publications Inc
17. Instituti i Statistikave http://www.instat.gov.al/media/2476/shqiperia_ne_shifra_2010.pdf
18. *Journal Java* 2012. Open Date Albania 2012 <https://ndiqparate.al/?p=6549>.
19. *Journal Telegrafe* July 13, 2012
20. Christen, K. Coastal Pollution Linked to Farms and Cities. *Water Environment & Technology*, 2002.14(4), 14–15. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24669163>
21. *Journal shekulli* 15.06.2021